

MONITORING LAND RESOURCES USING REMOTE SENSING

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This article presents the results of land resource monitoring using GIS and remote sensing systems. Maps of various types have been created, including the development of a unified electronic cartographic base and Earth remote sensing data.

Keywords: land resources, information support, agricultural map, geoinformation technologie.

Introduction. The Republic of Kazakhstan possesses 270.1 million hectares of land, of which 220 million hectares are used for agricultural purposes — the only natural source of livelihood for people. Land serves as the foundation for all processes of human activity in political, economic, social, industrial, legal, environmental, and other spheres. Possessing an enormous land resource potential, Kazakhstan must approach its use consciously — developing a strategy for the rational use and protection of land resources.

Under these conditions, to organize a space-based monitoring system of agricultural lands, which involves the prompt acquisition and thematic processing of large volumes of spatial data, it is necessary to employ wide-coverage satellite systems.

At present, the integration of new satellite systems has significantly expanded the range of tasks solved through space monitoring. The list of space monitoring tasks for Kazakhstan's agricultural lands includes assessing the sown area of spring crops and fallow fields; monitoring the timing of spring sowing; evaluating the condition and weed infestation of grain crops; forecasting grain yields one month in advance; and monitoring the timing and extent of harvesting operations. These activities are carried out in the main grain-producing regions of Kazakhstan — Akmola, Kostanay, North Kazakhstan, Karaganda, Pavlodar, and Almaty regions — where the main cultivated crops are spring wheat and barley.

High accuracy and efficiency of these operations are achieved through the use of modern GIS technologies. Every year, within the framework of the developed GIS systems, attribute information for each field in every region is updated, which makes it possible to perform various types of GIS analysis and to store the field history for all years of monitoring.

At present, an information system for monitoring and rational use of land resources is in operation. It was developed by the Center for Reception and Processing of Space Information of the Institute of Space Research in cooperation with the State Agency for Land Resources of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

To assess the condition of grain crops and forecast yields, agro-meteorological conditions, data from stationary test sites and ground surveys, as well as the distribution of satellite vegetation indices are analyzed. One of the challenges in yield forecasting from space is

the presence of weeds in the green biomass of grain crops. To address this factor, a technology has been developed to assess the degree of weed infestation and account for its impact on future yields.

In recent years, practice has shown that the use of satellite data plays an important role in providing the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Kazakhstan with up-to-date statistical and cartographic information.

The availability of such an objective information source enables management to monitor certain parameters of grain production (sown areas, crop rotation, phytosanitary condition, and yield) in the main grain-producing regions of the country. As a result, conditions are created for establishing economic transparency in grain production, which contributes to its self-regulation and the development of market relations in the agricultural sector of the national economy.

In the future, it is planned to expand the territorial scope of space monitoring of agricultural lands. It is expected that the system will also cover the western and southern regions, including winter cereals, industrial, and oilseed crops in the list of monitored fields. In addition, assessments of the condition and productivity of Kazakhstan's pastures will be conducted.

As a new direction for the application of space technologies in Kazakhstan, it is planned to develop an information support system for precision agriculture based on high-precision satellite navigation and data from the upcoming national remote sensing satellite system. When developing methods for crop yield forecasting, it is necessary to distinguish between key concepts such as potential or possible yield, actually attainable yield, and actual yield of agricultural crops. When using remote sensing data, the focus is on methods for forecasting the actually attainable yield, which are based on the use of the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI).

Joint research conducted by scientists from Israel, the USA, and Kazakhstan during 2000–2024 has shown that the dynamics of NDVI values (Fig. 1) correlate well with factors characterizing vegetation productivity (such as the amount of green biomass, stem density, and canopy coverage) across almost the entire territory of Kazakhstan.

Среднее содержание значений NDVI

Fig. 1 – Seasonal dynamics of vegetation condition in the territory of Kazakhstan (2021)

Based on a comprehensive analysis of remote sensing data and ground observations, a transition is made from NDVI values to indicators of above-ground biomass volume and the forecast of expected yield (Fig. 2).

During the experiment, the following were obtained: radiometric characteristics of all agricultural

lands over time, assessment of crop condition by the degree of pest damage, disease infestation, and weed contamination, as well as complete coordinate data of the test sites for synchronous under-satellite observations.

Fig. 2 – Dynamics of biomass growth across the territory of Kazakhstan

Preliminary processing of satellite images was carried out, and two-dimensional digital models of the test sites were created and aligned with cartographic base maps. Experimental data were obtained for the development of a methodology for monitoring biomass

condition and forecasting grain crop yields based on satellite imagery, remote sensing, and ground observations (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 – Map of Soil Fertility in Kazakhstan

Experimental data were obtained for developing a methodology to monitor biomass condition and forecast grain crop yields using satellite imaging, remote sensing, and ground-based observations. Agro-climatic zoning of the territory of Kazakhstan was performed based on long-term low-resolution remote sensing data from artificial Earth satellites.

Experimental data have been obtained for developing a methodology to monitor biomass conditions and forecast grain crop yields based on satellite imagery, remote sensing, and ground-based observations. Agroclimatic zoning of Kazakhstan's territory has been carried out using long-term low-resolution remote sensing data from satellites. The results of ground-based observations are used as training datasets for classification models and for testing their applicability in thematic interpretation, as well as for verifying methods used in applied monitoring tasks.

Conclusions.

The correspondence between ground surveys in the North Kazakhstan region during 2000–2024 and the recognition results of grain crop fields from satellite data is 97%. Analysis of the 3% error rate showed that inaccuracies were mainly due to a lack of “cloud-free”

data or significant deviations in the calendar dates of major agricultural operations. To assess the condition of grain crops and forecast yields, agrometeorological conditions, data from stationary test plots and ground-based route surveys, and the distribution of satellite vegetation indices are analyzed.

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